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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF HEPATITIS B AND HEPATITIS C
INFECTION IN PATIENTS ADMITTED IN VARIOUS
SURGICAL WARDS AT NISHTAR HOSPITAL MULTAN**¹Muhammad Salman, ²Yamna Khalid, ³Dr. Hafiz Zafar Ullah¹Medical officer Rural Health Center 134 GB Tehsil Samundri District Faisalabad, ²WMO Rehman Medical Complex, Nishtar Road, Multan, ³House Officer, Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan.

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Abstract:

Objective: This study is to evaluate the prevalence of hepatitis B (HBV) & hepatitis C virus (HCV) infections and its associated risk factors in patients admitted for surgical treatment at a tertiary care centre in Multan Pakistan.

Methodology: Four hundred and six patients admitted for various surgical procedures at Nishtar hospital Multan were screened for HBV and HCV. Patients of either gender, with above twenty years of age were included. Screening for HBV surface antigen (HBsAg) antibodies against HCV (anti-HCV) was performed through chromatography method. Blood samples that were repeatedly reactive for HBsAg or anti-HCV were considered positive.

Results: Out of 406 registered patients, 289 (71.1%) were male and 117 (28.8%) female. The overall seroprevalence of HBV infection within the study period was 4.3%, HCV 13.1%, and for HBV and HCV both was 3.7%. Regarding the etiological factors, previous history of blood transfusion was present in 10.46% patients, needle injection 93.02%, barber shaving 24.18%, and 20.93% patients had past history of surgery.

Conclusion: For the repression of transmission of HBV & HCV infection, the awareness in community regarding risk factors for spread of HCV and vaccination of hepatitis B and implementation of screening of both hepatitis B and C on large scale should be ensured.

Key Words: Hepatitis B and C, Risk Factors, Prevention, Multan, Pakistan.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis B and C virus has become a universally established health challenge due to its worldwide distribution, chronic persistence and complications. Hepatitis C virus was first discovered in 1988.¹ HBV and HCV infections are found to be present in blood of recipients, shaving by barbers, and after undergoing a dental procedure.² About 8 to 16 million Hepatitis B virus and 2.3 to 4.7 million Hepatitis C virus infections may occur per year from unprotected injections.³ The signs and symptoms of HBV & HCV infections are usually the abdominal pain, malaise, yellow discoloration i.e., jaundice. ⁴ Hepatitis C viruses can also present as silent infection, and persist for over 10 to 30 years without revealing symptoms. ⁵ Complications of HBV & HCV are portal hypertension, ascitis, esophageal varices and Cirrhosis.⁶

According to one of the global surveys, about 2 billion patients are infected with hepatitis B virus, 7,8 and over 350 million of population is a carrier of HBV.⁹ In India Hepatitis B virus infection is around 3-4%, and chronic hepatitis B infections is reported in above 50% of chronic hepatitis cases.¹⁰ In Hiroshima Japan, the virulence of HBV infection is 2.78 per 100,000 populations per year and with HCV infection about 1.86 per 100,000 populations per year.¹¹ In China about 10% of China's total population is affected from Hepatitis B virus infection.¹²

In Pakistan, Hepatitis B infected population is estimated about 7 million.¹³ In a study from Hafiz Abad, Pakistan, HBV prevalence was around 4.3% and HCV infection is present in 6.5% of the total studied populace.¹⁴ In a survey from northern region of Pakistan, about 2.5% of blood donors were having HBV, and around 5.1% had HCV.¹⁵ Worldwide Seroprevalence of HCV is estimated about a hundred and seventy million of populace per year & the spread of 3 to 4 million.¹⁶

METHODOLOGY:**Study Area:**

This descriptive hospital based study was conducted between August 2016 and February 2017 at Nishtar

Hospital Multan. The pathological laboratory is present in the hospital premises. All patients above twenty years of age, with either sex, having no documented previous history of CLD, Hepatitis B Virus or Hepatitis C Virus infection, admitted for different surgical procedures were included. Patients that required urgent surgical intervention were not included in this study. The patients were interviewed on a preformed questionnaire regarding age, gender, address, literacy level, blood transfusions, shaving history from barber shops, and any previous history of surgery, family history etc.

Method of screening for HBV and HCV: A 2-3 milliliter venous blood sample was collected by aseptically into a sterile test tube from each patient and tested for Hepatitis B surface antigen and anti HCV antibodies within 24 hours of blood collection. The screening was done through a rapid chromatography immunoassay for qualitative detection of HBsAg for HBV and Anti HCV antibodies for hepatitis-C virus, using a kit, Accurate / Acou device (Made IN USA). All of the investigations were performed under the supervision of a pathologist.

Samples that were positive for either HBV or HCV were tested again for a second time by exactly same method. Samples that were repeatedly reactive for Hepatitis B surface antigen or anti- HCV were considered positive. The subjects positive for HBV or HCV were referred to the department of Medicine, Nishtar Hospital Multan for further management.

RESULTS:

A total of four hundred and six (406) admitted patients under went screening process for Hepatitis B and Hepatitis C Viruses. The characteristics of this study population are mentioned in Table-I. Hepatitis B and C viral infection was detected in eighty six (21.18%) patients out of 406. The overall seroprevalence of Hepatitis B Virus infection within this study period was in 17 patients (4.18%), for Hepatitis C Virus infection in 53 patients (13.05%), and both HBV and HCV infections in 16 patients (3.94%). Details regarding seroprevalence of HBV & HCV are shown in Figure 1 while risk factors are given in Table-II.

Characteristics	No. of patients	(%)
Gender		
Male	289	71.1
Female	117	28.8
Age		
20-30	17	4.18
31-40	34	8.37
41-50	187	46.05
51-60	111	27.33
Above 60	57	14.03
Residency		
Rural	238	58.6
Urban	168	41.37
Literacy		
Literate	134	33
Illiterate	272	66.99
Socio Economic Status		
Middle lower	92	22.66
Lower	314	77.33

Risk Factors / History of	Number of individuals exposed
Blood Transfusion	9 (10.46%)
Needle Injections	80 (93.02%)
Barber Shaving	21 (24.41%)
Past H/o Surgery	18 (20.93%)

Figure 1: Seroprevalence of Hepatitis B and C (N=86)

DISCUSSION:

The burden of Hepatitis B & C infection is increasing worldwide and Pakistan is also not exempted. Punjab, which is a province in Pakistan, has a population of around 110 million. The rural proportion of Punjab is 63.6% of total population of Punjab. 17 In a retrospective study from Pakistan, the prevalence of Hepatitis B in Lahore i.e., the capital city of Punjab in 1999 was 5.05%, while in Karachi, prevalence in 2000 was 5.46% and later, in 2004 was increased to 5.83%, prevalence in Rawalpindi in the year 2002 was 3.53% and in Islamabad in 2004 was 2.56%.¹⁸ Collectively the prevalence of HBV in Pakistan was revealed from 3.16% to 10.4% in different surveys conducted at various places in Pakistan.¹⁹ In this research the prevalence of HBV alone was 4.18%. WHO estimated that about 67 million new cases of HBV infections occur every year worldwide. 20

The seroprevalence of Hepatitis C Virus is around 14.4% in southern Italy, ²¹ while in adult populace of Japan is 0.4%. In Turkey the seroprevalence of Hepatitis C infection is about 2.4%.²² According to one of many surveys, approximately 10 million of population in Pakistan (6% of total population) are suffering from HCV infection.^{23,24}

In a retrospective national study from Pakistan, the seroprevalence of Hepatitis C Virus in Karachi in the year 2003 was about 2.2%, while in Lahore city in 2004 was 13.5%, Rawalpindi in year 2005 was having a population of 11.26%.²¹ The prevalence of HCV in Buner, city of NWFP, Pakistan was about 4.57% in general.²⁵ In our study, the seroprevalence for HCV infection was 13.05%, while the prevalence of dual infection by Hepatitis B Virus and Hepatitis C Virus infection in this study was 3.94%, as compared to a similar study from India, where prevalence of this infection was 5%.²⁶

CONCLUSION:

Timely identification of population suffering from Hepatitis B virus or Hepatitis C Virus infection is essential to prevent the rapid spread of HBV and HCV infection in Pakistan. Special consideration should initialize including training of medical and paramedical staff, community awareness on a larger scale, proper methods of sterilization of surgical instruments, proper use of gloving, and proper

disposal of used syringes and needles in order to prevent our future generations from HBV & HCV.

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